

Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of (*N*-phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-substituted-azetidin)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

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Manuscript received 27 December 2006, revised 3 October 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : (*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-substituted-azetidin)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (**2a-s**) have been synthesised by cycloaddition of (*N*-phenothiazinomethyl)-4-(arylideneamino)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (**1a-s**) with chloro ketene generated *in situ* from chloroacetyl chloride and triethylamine. All the products have been evaluated *in vitro* for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against some selected microbes and *in vivo* for their antiinflammatory activity by rat paw oedema method.

Keywords : Phenothiazinomerapto-1,2,4-triazoles, antimicrobial, antiinflammatory activities.

Introduction

Phenothiazine with 2-azetidinones have been synthesised for a wide range of industrial, pharmaceutical and biological purposes¹⁻⁴. In continuation of earlier work we have synthesized the new compounds containing phenothiazine and azetidinone nuclei in one frame work (**2a-s**) (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

Antimicrobial activity : Compounds **2a-s** were screened for their antibacterial activity⁵ against gram (+) bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* (*Bs*) and gram (-) bacteria *Escherichia coli* (*Ec*) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*Kp*) and antifungal activity⁵ against *Aspergillus niger* (*An*), *Aspergillus flavus* (*Af*) and *Candida albicans* (*Ca*) at 100 ppm concentration using gentamicin and griseofulvin as standards for comparison under similar conditions for antibacterial and antifungal activities respectively. The following compounds were found active against the noted bacteria and fungi : **2b** (*An*, *Af*, *Ca*), **2c** (*Bs*, *Ec*, *Kp*), **2d** (*Bs*, *Ec*, *Kp*, *An*, *Af*, *Ca*) and **2g** (*Bs*, *Ec*, *Kp*).

Antiinflammatory activity : Compounds **2a-s** (100 mg/kg b.w.) were tested for their antiinflammatory activity in albino rats of either sex (100–150 g) by the reported method⁶ using phenylbutazone (100 mg/kg b.w.) as a standard. Compounds **2b**, **2c**, **2d** and **2k** showed 45, 40, 40 and 40% inhibition in comparison to standard (50%).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu

8416 FTIR (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}), ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker DRX 300 in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 FAB instrument. Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC (silica gel) plates. All the compounds gave satisfactory analytical data m.p.s are in °C.

1,2 a R₁ = H; R₂ = C₆H₅

b R₁ = H; R₂ = 2-ClC₆H₄

c R₁ = H; R₂ = 3-ClC₆H₄

d R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-ClC₆H₄

e R₁ = H; R₂ = 2-BrC₆H₄

f R₁ = H; R₂ = 3-BrC₆H₄

g R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-BrC₆H₄

h R₁ = H; R₂ = 2-NO₂C₆H₄

i R₁ = H; R₂ = 3-NO₂C₆H₄

j R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-NO₂C₆H₄

k R₁ = H; R₂ = 2-CH₃OC₆H₄

l R₁ = H; R₂ = 3-CH₃OC₆H₄

m R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-CH₃OC₆H₄

n R₁ = H; R₂ = *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄

o R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = C₆H₅

p R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = 2-ClC₆H₄

q R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = 3-ClC₆H₄

r R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = 4-ClC₆H₄

s R₁ = R₂ = C₆H₅

Scheme 1

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-phenylazetidin)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2a** :

A mixture of (*N*-phenothiazinomethyl)-4-(phenylamino)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **1a** (1.1 mol) in dry acetone (30 ml) was kept at room temperature for

about 24 h. The mixture was first stirred (30 min) and then refluxed for about 6 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from acetone to give **2a**, m.p. 140–142°; ν_{\max} 3027, 1582, 1559, 1470, 860, 708 (phenothiazine nucleus), 2607 (SH), 1780 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1460 (N-CH₂), 743 (C-Cl); δ 6.63–7.10 (13H, m, Ar-H), 5.13 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, CHCl), 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 3.50 (1H, s, SH), 3.17 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, N-CH); FAB-MS, *m/z* 491 (M⁺), 463, 371, 279, 251, 223, 212, 208, 198, 152, 117, 71.

The compounds **2b-s** were synthesized by the similar method from **1b-s**.

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(2-chlorophenyl)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2b** : m.p. 160–162°; ν_{\max} 3030, 1580, 1555, 1468, 878, 700, 2600, 1775, 1622, 1462, 752 (Ar-Cl); δ 6.69–7.15, 5.18, 3.62, 3.46, 3.19; FAB-MS, *m/z* 526 (M⁺), 497, 313, 311, 285, 257, 242, 212, 198, 186, 151, 71; **2c**, m.p. 168–169°; **2d**, m.p. 147–148°.

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(2-bromophenyl)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2e** : m.p. 189–191°; ν_{\max} 3025, 1585, 1552, 1465, 870, 710, 2610, 1772, 1625, 1458, 621 (Ar-Br); δ 6.70–7.13, 5.12, 3.65, 3.48, 3.17; FAB-MS, *m/z* 570 (M⁺), 542, 358, 311, 302, 224, 212, 198, 196, 117, 71; **2f**, m.p. 176–177°; **2g**, m.p. 153–155°.

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(2-nitrophenyl)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2h** : m.p. 132–134°; ν_{\max} 3033, 1570, 1555, 1470, 872, 702, 2598, 1770, 1619, 1450, 1345, (Ar-NO₂); δ 6.60–7.00, 4.98, 3.60, 3.51, 3.20; FAB-MS, *m/z* 536 (M⁺), 449, 324, 311, 296, 267, 259, 225, 212, 198, 162, 71; **2i**, m.p. 140–141°; **2j**, m.p. 124–126°.

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(2-methoxyphenyl)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2k** : m.p. 190–193°; ν_{\max} 3033, 1575, 1552, 1478, 872, 703, 2871 and 1164 (Ar-CH₃O), 2615, 1769, 1626, 1452; δ 6.89–7.10, 5.03, 3.85, 3.62, 3.50, 3.21, 3.95 (3H, s, 1 ×

CH₃O); FAB-MS, *m/z* 521 (M⁺), 479, 311, 282, 281, 274, 253, 212, 210, 198, 182, 71; **2l**, m.p. 182–183°; **2m**, m.p. 1981–199°.

(*N*-Phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2n** : m.p. 153–155°; ν_{\max} 3020, 1575, 1552, 1482, 855, 700, 2609, 1773, 1621, 1452, 2910 and 2852 (N-CH₃); δ 6.69–7.15, 5.10, 3.70, 3.59, 3.18, 1.92 (6H, s, N-Me₂); FAB-MS, *m/z* 502 (M⁺), 322, 311, 294, 266, 251, 212, 198, 195, 120, 71; **2o**, m.p. 147–149°.

(*N*-phenothiazinomethyl)-4-[*N*-(3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(2-chloroacetophenone)azetidyl)]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole, **2p** : m.p. 133–135°; ν_{\max} 3045, 1576, 1551, 1482, 862, 706, 2618, 1775, 1625, 1453, 760 (Ar-Cl), 2918 and 2859 (CH₃); δ 6.95–7.20, 4.92, 3.62, 3.58, 1.85 (3H, s, 1 × CH₃); FAB-MS, *m/z* 540 (M⁺), 512, 321, 311, 300, 272, 257, 212, 207, 198, 166, 71; **2q**, m.p. 117–118°; **2r**, m.p. 122–124°; **2s**, m.p. 150–153°.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow for providing spectral and analytical data of the compounds. Authors are also thankful to the Heads, Department of Botany and Department of Microbiology for providing the facility for biological screening and Chemistry for facility.

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